

Towards Gratitude-Oriented Approach
Shaping Questions with Solution-Focused Brief Therapy
for a Group-Based Mobile App

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Abstract

A recent literature review suggested that gratitude is an underappreciated way to respond to socio-psychological stress in today's world. Growing evidence shows widespread interest in gratitude interventions and highlights mobile apps as an effective, low-cost, scalable way to deliver them. At the same time, preliminary findings propose that social group contexts, such as social networking platforms, can amplify the benefits of gratitude. However, it's been noted that mental health apps often lack user-centric design, and it has been emphasized that apps should better adapt to diverse user contexts. In response, this paper explores combining ideas from gratitude interventions with solution-focused brief therapy to shape reflective questions for a group-based mobile app. That may enable more user-centric design that adapts to a diverse range of user goals. This also addresses a research gap to establish best practices to design digital group-based intervention.

Keywords:

gratitude, solution-focused brief therapy, group solution-focused brief therapy, mental health apps

Zusammenfassung

Eine aktuelle Literaturübersicht legt nahe, dass Dankbarkeit ein bislang unterschätzter Weg ist, um auf sozial-psychologischen Stress in der heutigen Welt zu reagieren. Zunehmende Evidenz zeigt ein breites Interesse an Dankbarkeitsinterventionen und hebt hervor, dass mobile Apps ein effektives, kostengünstiges und skalierbares Mittel zu deren Umsetzung darstellen. Gleichzeitig deuten vorläufige Befunde darauf hin, dass soziale Gruppenkontexte, wie sie soziale Netzwerke bieten, die Wirkung von Dankbarkeit verstärken können. Allerdings wurde festgestellt, dass mentale Gesundheits-Apps häufig nicht nutzerzentriert gestaltet sind, und es wurde betont, dass Apps besser auf unterschiedliche Nutzungskontexte abgestimmt werden sollten. Als Reaktion darauf untersucht diese Arbeit die Kombination von Ansätzen aus Dankbarkeitsinterventionen mit lösungsfokussierter Kurztherapie, um reflektierende Fragen für eine gruppenbasierte mobile App zu gestalten. Dies könnte eine nutzerzentriertere Gestaltung ermöglichen, die sich an einer Vielzahl von Nutzerzielen orientiert. Gleichzeitig adressiert dies eine Forschungslücke zur Etablierung von Best Practices für digitale gruppenbasierte Interventionen.

Schlüsselwörter:

Dankbarkeit, lösungsorientierte Kurzzeittherapie, lösungsorientierte Gruppenkurzzeittherapie, Apps für psychische Gesundheit

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Introduction

Mental health apps are increasingly supported by evidence. They are low-cost and scalable digital tools for treating and preventing so-called psychological disorders (Linardon et al., 2024). A recent meta-analysis (Luo et al., 2025) reviewed 46 studies evaluating mobile mental health apps for depression, involving over 4,000 participants. The results showed small to medium effect sizes for symptom reduction. Another recent meta-analysis (Linardon et al., 2024) concluded that mental health smartphone apps are effective for symptoms of depression and anxiety.

Public interest in mental health apps is growing. More and more apps are available (Linardon et al., 2024). Young adults increasingly turn to apps for mental health support, describing them as “efficient and helpful” (Holtz et al., 2025). There is growing public interest in those tools (Linardon et al., 2024).

Despite being recognized as useful and desirable tools, mental health apps still require improvement. Alqahtani & Orji (2020) suggests that users often stop using mental health apps too early to fully receive the benefits of using them. They analyzed 13,549 reviews of 106 mental health apps. Using thematic analysis, they set out to find what users liked and disliked about them. Users report liking a good user interface, a variety of features and content, and the ability to adapt the apps to their preferences. Users named poor usability as the most common factor for abandoning apps. Other issues were lack of content variety, limited personalization, lack of customer service, low trust, security, and privacy concerns.

This review of 106 mental health apps also found that most of the apps did not disclose the clinical expertise of the people involved in their development (Alqahtani & Orji, 2020). This suggests that many apps were created without involving mental health professionals. Lack of a clinical input may explain why some apps appear to rely on simplified versions of evidence-based interventions without adapting to users diverse contexts. Along with as a suggestion that a better user experience of mental health apps predicts better mental health outcomes (Kalon et al., 2025), this highlights a need for better design that adapts to a more diverse range of user goals, guided by psychotherapeutic approaches.

Among the variety of mental health apps, gratitude-based apps represent a promising direction. They are presented as a user-friendly, low-cost, scalable, and flexible way to

practice gratitude (Prabawa et al., 2025). Huge interest in gratitude interventions by the public is reported (Kalon et al., 2025), along with a recognition that gratitude is an underappreciated way that can help current society respond to “socio-psychological stress uniquely relevant in today’s fractured world.” (Prabawa et al., 2025)

Gratitude interventions may have stronger effects in groups. Preliminary findings propose that social group contexts, such as social networking platforms, can amplify the benefits of gratitude (Sciara et al., 2021). Theory of social learning also suggests that by observing someone else engaging in gratitude practices, others might learn to imitate them (Bandura, 1977) and receive benefits from practicing gratitude. That could amplify gratitude effects when practiced in groups.

An app called Gratitude Club was developed in 2025 by the author of this thesis. The app adapted questions from the “Gratitude Works!” (Emmons, 2013) book by a prominent researcher in the field. Members were invited to share answers to those questions with the group. Members saw what everybody shared and interacted with each other by liking and commenting on each other’s posts.

Mixed feedback was reported. Members described the app as helpful in cultivating a habit of noticing more good things around them. Reflections from others were perceived as reminders to slow down and stay grateful. Several comments addressed the reflective questions. Some participants wished for more open-ended questions instead of the current questions that were sometimes considered too specific. A bigger variety of questions was requested. Words such as “forced” and “pushed” were mentioned in the feedback, proposing that members sometimes felt strongly guided by the questions. Lack of an engaged community along with anxiety to share vulnerable reflections were mentioned as well. All the identified concerns might suggest a partial mismatch between individual goals and the question’s direction. This can be read as a call for better facilitation with more adaptive questions.

Overall, literature proposes that mental health apps in general and gratitude mobile apps in particular are helpful tools. While practicing gratitude in digital communities might amplify the benefits, feedback suggests that better questions are needed.

One possible solution is to integrate Solution-Focused Brief Therapy. This approach demonstrated itself as an effective therapeutic choice for diverse psychological, social,

learning, medical, couple, or self-related challenges (Žak & Pečala, 2025). Additionally, its main principles seem similar to gratitude interventions. Integration might create an approach that addresses a broader range of people's goals while still satisfying the demand of practicing gratitude. The combined use of solution-focused brief therapy with gratitude interventions was not found in existing literature. Literature on integrating group solution-focused brief therapy into mobile apps was not found also. To address the gap in the literature, this thesis addresses the following research question: *How can solution-focused brief therapy shape gratitude-oriented reflective questions for a group-based mobile app?*

To shape new questions, the thesis proceeds as follows. First, ideas of solution-focused brief therapy, group solution-focused therapy, and gratitude interventions will be reviewed. At the end of each section, example reflective questions that can be asked in each approach will be discussed. Next, what's known about relevant digital interventions will be reviewed along with example questions that are used in them. In the last chapter, possible ways of integrating the approaches into a group-based mobile app will be explored, and example questions of a new integrated approach will be presented.

1 Relevant Approaches for Mental Health Apps

In this chapter, main ideas from gratitude interventions, solution-focused brief therapy, and group solution-focused therapy will be reviewed. Solution-focused brief therapy and gratitude interventions will be referred to as approaches. The effectiveness of both approaches will be reviewed. At the end of each section, examples of questions that each approach employs will be listed and connected back to the main principles of the approaches. When discussing gratitude interventions, perspectives from different thinkers will be discussed.

1.1 Gratitude Interventions

In this section, gratitude interventions will be discussed. First, the definition of gratitude interventions and one model that conceptualizes them will be chosen and reviewed. Then, what's known about the effectiveness of gratitude interventions will be addressed. Next, a look at how different thinkers conceptualized gratitude will be discussed. The section will be concluded with example questions that are used in different gratitude interventions.

1.1.1 Definition

The following definition of gratitude is accepted in this paper: "Gratitude is the life orientation toward noticing and appreciating the positive in the world" (Sciara et al., 2021). Gratitude orientation to life might come with feelings of gratitude, but it is not necessary (Emmons & McCullough, 2004).

Emmons (2024) proposes the so-called ARC model of gratitude. He says that gratitude amplifies, rescues, and connects. Now each component will be discussed and connected to other known research.

Gratitude amplifies. Positive things we see about ourselves, others, and the world in general become bigger. The more we practice gratitude, the more positive things we notice (Emmons, 2024). Knowing what we know about social learning theory (Bandura, 1977) and emotional contagion (Sciara et al., 2021), we might additionally assume that gratitude amplifies not only the amount of good we see but also the amount of good that is actually happening. When we share what good we see, others might learn to do the same,

and because people might feel good and act more helpful towards those who express it or towards those who receive the gratitude. Also, people tend to act more prosocially when they feel grateful (Diniz et al., 2022). Besides, when we notice good, we feel good (Diniz et al., 2022), and we learn and create better according to the broaden-and-build theory (Fredrickson, 2004). As we see, gratitude amplifies good things in life in various ways.

Gratitude rescues. Emmons (2024) writes that left to itself, our mind tends to pay attention to negativity and hijacks our happiness. By focusing on what's good, on people, not on ourselves, we feel less anxiety (Diniz et al., 2022) and we ruminate less (Kalon et al., 2025).

Gratitude connects. Emmons (2024) argues that human relationships would break down without gratitude. He argues that gratitude is a “moral cement, the all-purpose glue, the emotional fillings” that connects us to each other. It connects organizations, families, and societies. Even Adam Smith, who is famous for arguing that individuals are driven by self-interest, recognized that humans are linked to each other through passions and affections, and that is required for the flourishing of society (Harpham, 2004).

If gratitude is about noticing and appreciating good in the world, and doing that amplifies the good, rescues us from anxiety and rumination, and connects humans to each other, what is *gratitude intervention*?

Diniz et al. (2022) in their systematic review writes that by gratitude interventions, they mean many activities such as:

- writing gratitude reflections in diaries
- expressing gratitude verbally or in writing
- posting pictures on social media with words of gratitude.

My paper will define *gratitude intervention* as any activity that an individual does with an intention to notice and appreciate good things in life.

1.1.2 Effectiveness

Diniz et al. (2022) made a systematic review and a meta-analysis of gratitude intervention effects. This is the result of the meta-analysis.

People who underwent gratitude interventions experienced:

- more gratitude
- greater satisfaction with life
- better mental health
- fewer symptoms of anxiety and depression
- more positive mood
- more prosocial behavior

Diniz et al. (2022) also notes that gratitude can be beneficial to a wide range of people. From students to prisoners. From children to adults. Across different contexts, cultures, ages, professions, and health statuses. This confirms that gratitude interventions can be beneficial to a general population.

Prabawa et al. (2025) also writes that gratitude interventions are an effective and low-cost method to enhance both individual well-being and promote collective resilience.

Kalon et al. (2025), summarizing recent findings, lists several promising aspects of gratitude interventions for a general population. First, they found huge interest in using the intervention and found that people are likely to recommend such interventions to friends. They also noted that gratitude interventions are easy to practice, enjoyable, focused on less stigmatizing content, and help people learn not to neglect the positive but to expand their attention to it.

1.1.3 Perspectives

Findings on gratitude interventions seem to be very optimistic. In my private conversations with friends and users of my other mobile app that focuses directly on cultivating gratitude, it was also mostly positive. One can find similarities between being so into gratitude and being in love. When you fall in love, you stop seeing nuances and idealize the object. This might also be happening to me as a researcher of this topic, and to respond to this, I thought it might be very important to find out what other perspectives there are on gratitude.

At the same time, in my other private conversations about gratitude, I've heard concerns about practicing gratitude. For example, one of my friends expressed how gratitude can be misused:

My initial perception of gratitude practices was that it was often discussed in women's groups. That as the source I took MAJOR issue with because I think it's often how women's groups dodge addressing the impacts of sexism on the group members. If a woman is really frustrated about her husband or not getting promoted at work, we're supposed to focus on the gratitude practice to help us move past it. I know enough about the practice to know that it's a "yes and" not an "either or" choice.

I think that as women, our anger and our being indignant is necessary to mobilize us to create change. So the effort to pacify a woman in that scenario (and frankly there are other examples that are the same where this is used on men who someone wants to keep quiet) serve multiple purposes, and not all of them are good nor in line with the interests of the person receiving the guidance.

(Rachel Fetrow, personal communication, February 11, 2026)

In some other private communications, people expressed that although they don't write a gratitude journal per se, they write down warm moments of their day. This is, for example, what a user of my other journaling app says:

I'm not skeptical [about the practice of gratitude], it's just that it doesn't really do anything for me. Or maybe I just haven't gotten around to keeping a gratitude journal yet. But noting something so warm, something meaningful that happened during the day—I enjoy that! Perhaps that's my form of gratitude. Maybe it just looks that way, as if it were being channeled into the atmosphere, into the universe. I notice that I have a lot of entries like, "I'm grateful to life that this actually happened, that this opportunity fell to me."

(Caterina, personal communication, February 13, 2026)

Concerns about gratitude interventions are to be found in literature also. Lei et al. (2025) reports that people are not clear on the reasons why they need to cultivate gratitude. Diniz et al. (2022) adds that it is difficult to express.

But what is gratitude? What did different thinkers write about it in the past?

Harpham (2004) writes that Roman Stoic philosopher Seneca, for example, in his “On Benefits,” noted that gratitude arises as a response to a benefit that was freely given. Seneca remarked that if the intention of a giver is to receive something back or make a receiver feel bad, then gratitude is not needed. A gift, in his view, is given out of desire to assist another human being. Additionally, he notes that Seneca emphasized that if a receiver expresses gratitude out of guilt, anger, or duty, then the debt of gratitude wasn’t fulfilled.

This idea is echoed in Marshall Rosenberg’s “Nonviolent Communication” (2012). He argues that when we express gratitude to get something back, it might work short-term, but once the manipulation is sensed, all the beauty of appreciation is spoiled. In his view, we need to express gratitude solely to celebrate the ways our life is better because of the actions of others. On receiving gratitude, Rosenberg proposed that it might be a good idea to simply listen to the feelings and needs that have been fulfilled as a result of our actions, without false superiority or false humility.

Harpham (2004) when interpreting philosopher Thomas Hobbes’s *Leviathan*, conceptualized gratitude as something that isn’t only about the relationship between two people but rather something that benefits and strengthens the society in general. This involves prompting individuals to act in ways that do not benefit them directly but benefit others and society in general.

Modern philosopher Barbara Herman, in her *The Moral Habitat* (2021), discussed many complications of gratitude. She notes that in some cases, a simple thank-you note is enough, and the so-called duty is paid, but in others, the first benefit creates an open-ended sequence of reciprocation. It can be more complicated because if somebody helps somebody in need, they can unintentionally create a potential “rainy day fund.” Potential in case the receiver of initial help can help in the same way in the future. Whether you meant it that way doesn’t change the presence of this complication. But what if that person can pay it back in an equal value? Can they pay less, Herman wonders. Or if the initial receiver can’t pay the initial giver, can somebody else be helped instead?

Sometimes one does something for another and receives gratitude, and for a moment the debt of gratitude is paid. But if a similar situation arises where the initial receiver can help the initial giver, the reciprocity is found to be open again, Herman writes. But

then also, who do we express gratitude to and return the favor to if we have been helped anonymously? She brings up complications yet again.

Additionally, she discusses the possible dependency that can come up along with gratitude and reciprocation. If someone got help, she explains, it might create some dependency that one can find troubling, and expressing gratitude might be a way to restore the balance. Or somebody might not even accept a gift to keep their autonomy.

To conclude, Herman (2021) presents gratitude as one duty in the system of moral duties, building on ideas of Immanuel Kant. She presents gratitude as an *imperfect* duty. She says that we ought to be grateful, but we can choose how we can be grateful. Here, she gives us an active role. On the other hand, she says that humanity needs its humans to be good to each other. The duty of gratitude is included in a complex system of other duties that all represent the moral habitat we all live in.

A notable similarity between my friend's understanding of gratitude as a "yes and" approach that involves choice and Herman's approach that basically says that we ought to be grateful, but we can decide when and how we can practice appreciation.

A practical example of how this complicated system of duties can be approached that I found the most inspiring comes from the book *Reflections for Common Ground* by Beth Lincoln. In her description of the traditional extended family structures of African Americans, she writes, "Interdependence is not considered reciprocal, but rather open and fluid."

1.1.4 Questions Examples

After discussing definition, model, effectiveness, and different perspectives on gratitude and gratitude interventions, it seems appropriate to take a look at different questions that could be asked in order to cultivate gratitude. All the questions will come from *The Little Book of Gratitude* (Emmons, 2024). The questions will be connected to ideas about gratitude discussed earlier in this chapter.

The following adaptation of the classical Three Good Things exercise is mentioned in the book: "Think about three things that went well for you yesterday. Why did they go well? How grateful do they make you feel? Did you tell anyone about them?" These questions clearly promote noticing good things in life as per the definition of gratitude. One could also see how the author simply asks about feelings of gratitude, not pushing to make

people *feel* it, and also promotes sharing it with others, which can create or strengthen connections.

If ingratitude can be viewed as a moral offense, this is a question that invites people into a reflection on things that they might want to change: “Who have I harmed by my thoughtlessness or self-centeredness?”

Another example question, “How can you show gratitude for the many gifts you have received?” clearly gives freedom in ways someone can show gratitude. It’s worth noting that before connecting the idea of agency of how we can show gratitude, I felt “pushed” by that question. Knowing the context made a difference for me.

The next questions come after a list of metaphors: “Which one of the metaphors...most clearly captures your understanding of gratitude? Why?” Again, the question feels much more open than I previously thought before I did my reading. It’s a question that invites looking at the gratitude approach to life in general.

This is a good example of a relationship-focused question: “Who has lit the flame in you?” It directly asks about a person in life and invites us to notice, appreciate, and possibly connect with that person. It is also curiously different from the “Who do you feel grateful for today?” question that seems to be a very popular question to ask. Emmons (2024) writes that newness is important in gratitude, and it might be worth noticing how gratitude might surprise us, and he seems to use that principle in writing questions—he keeps them new and surprising.

This is a curious example that possibly brings a new context to searching for feelings of gratitude: “Is there somewhere that activates feelings of gratitude?” Some questions focus on people, some make a difference with a new wording, and this one invites us to think in a new direction—physical places where one is more likely to feel gratitude.

As my personal conclusion, the questions that are presented in this book (Emmons, 2024) are more diverse than what I would consider to be “classical” gratitude questions. They seemed more interesting to me because they are new to me. This might be a useful hypothesis—*we need new questions to provoke our thinking in new ways.*

1.2 Solution-Focused Brief Therapy

Prabawa et al. (2025) when reviewing the role of gratitude in different psychotherapeutic approaches, argues that gratitude is useful as a standalone intervention and as a part of a psychotherapeutic approach. When used in a psychotherapeutic context, mental health benefits increase because, in their view, gratitude intervention can help clients connect deeper with the topic. This suggests that combining solution-focused brief therapy and gratitude is not only possible but might be desirable. Therefore, solution-focused brief therapy will be reviewed in this chapter. Development, its main principles, and its effectiveness will be reviewed, and example questions that a solution-focused practitioner might ask will be discussed.

1.2.1 Development

Steve de Shazer, Insoo Kim Berg, and their colleagues at the Milwaukee Brief Family Therapy developed solution-focused brief therapy in the 1980s (McKergow & Korman, 2009). Solution-focused brief therapy was developed from observations of real sessions from behind a one-way mirror. Steve de Shazer, Insoo Kim Berg, and their colleagues noted the therapist's words and behavior that resulted in progress toward the client's stated goals. What helped become staple techniques and what didn't help was discarded (De Shazer et al., 2021).

The author's life histories and interests influenced the development of the approach. For example, Insoo Kim Berg moved to the USA from South Korea, lived through the Korean War, and experienced severe hardship and loss of loved ones (De Shazer et al., 2021). Another example of influence is the fact that Steve De Shazer was a Wittgensteinian scholar (De Shazer et al., 2021), which one can clearly see by the number of Wittgenstein citations in his books.

1.2.2 Main Principles

Solution-focused brief therapy was developed from practice to theory, and its authors claim not to have a big grounding theory explaining everything. They simply observed and noted what worked (De Shazer et al., 2021). Later, when they wrote books about

solution-focused brief therapy, they were able to formulate some main principles of the approach.

It seems important to first investigate what *solution-focused* means. Does a solution-focused practitioner suggest solutions right away? Is there any space to talk about problems? In “Interviewing for Solutions,” Berg & Jong (2012) gives us the context needed to answer those questions. Focus on solutions needs to be understood in contrast to focusing on problem-solving. Berg writes that in their view, this problem-solving was a dominant paradigm in the field. Practitioners believed that they needed to figure out what the client was suffering from and heal them. They criticized this paradigm and recommended another way.

Indeed, clients do come to therapy with their “problems”, although De Shazer et al. (2021) believed that solutions are not necessarily related to problems. In contrast with the problem-solving paradigm, clients in solution-focused brief therapy are assisted in creating an image of a future where the problem is no longer there and then look for moments in the present where this preferred future already exists even in a minimal form. These moments are called exceptions in SFBT terms, that is, situations in which the problem holds less space and the preferred future becomes more visible. This idea has little to do with the “origins” of the problem and focuses mostly on the present and future.

One of the main principles might be worded as such: *if there is no problem, there should be no therapy* (De Shazer et al., 2021). Therefore, solution-focused brief therapy doesn’t provide tools for “self-awareness,” it doesn’t go “deep,” and it prefers to help people and let them go without forming dependency.

Another important principle is *if it works, do more of it*. SFBT therapists encourage their clients to look at what is working in their lives (De Shazer et al., 2021).

Yet another principle is *if it doesn’t work, do something else*. This might sound almost naive, De Shazer et al. (2021) writes, but many other therapy schools overlook it. As an example of this principle, if a client doesn’t complete the task, it’s not thought of as “resistance.” Rather, a psychotherapist needs to offer something else (De Shazer et al., 2021). This “something else” obviously has limitations: a psychotherapist cannot offer to train a person in the gym, for example, but SFBT practitioners are asked to be flexible.

In SFBT, *questions* are the primary intervention. SFBT therapists usually do not in-

interpret, challenge, or confront their clients. Questions are asked from an assumption that people have strong resources and can use them to make changes. Questions are positioning clients as experts in their own lives (De Shazer et al., 2021).

SFBT therapists are listening to people in a special way. While it's still important to acknowledge a client's struggles and express natural empathy like in any other therapy school, SFBT therapists also always pay special attention to exceptions in a client's problems and opportunities to turn the conversation towards solutions (De Shazer et al., 2021).

To summarize, solution-focused practitioners, together with their clients, construct ideas of how a preferred future could look for the clients, find moments where this is already somehow happening, and see more resources that clients can use (Žak & Pečala, 2025).

1.2.3 Deliberate Omissions

McKergow & Korman (2009) suggest that another way to understand SFBT is to take a look at things solution-focused practitioners do *not* normally do at all:

1. They don't pay attention to what is wrong.
2. They don't assume that there are some internal issues that need to be found and transformed.
3. They don't use theories to "understand" the client.
4. They don't ask about what stops or blocks the client.

One can think of SFBT as a minimalist approach that questions the necessity of many accepted elements of a good therapy (McKergow & Korman, 2009). Why introduce complex terms if just using the client's words can be enough? Why assume that something is wrong or broken inside our clients? Why focus on what's going wrong, what stops the client, if we can go straight into constructing a solution? Why waste time and money?

1.2.4 Effectiveness

Is solution-focused brief therapy as effective as its founders hoped it to be? Žak & Pečala (2025) did an umbrella review of systematic reviews and meta-analyses of the approach.

They analyzed 25 systematic reviews, including 15 meta-analyses, and found significant positive outcomes across different issues, settings, and cultural contexts. These results will be discussed in this subsection.

The effectiveness of solution-focused brief therapy was established for depression, overall mental health, and progress towards individual goals for the adult population. Evidence included individual, group, couple/family, mixed, or other formats, such as applied in the classroom or by telephone. Curiously, the group format was more effective when applied in 6–10 sessions vs. more.

Importantly, no evidence of harm was found, and solution-focused brief therapy was found to be affordable for the public health system.

High confidence in the effectiveness of SFBT was found for internalizing issues, specifically for depression and overall mental health, based on evidence predominantly from Western countries. Eastern primary studies indicated moderate confidence.

Effectiveness in this review was established mainly in comparison to other therapeutic approaches, such as psychodynamic or cognitive–behavioral therapy in the studies of Western studies and in comparison to no treatment in Eastern studies.

1.2.5 Questions Examples

Previously, what solution-focused practitioners normally do and normally do not do at all were discussed. It was concluded that questions are the primary intervention of the approach. In this section, possible questions that solution-focused therapists might ask will be given and connected to the main principles. All the following questions were taken directly from De Shazer et al. (2021) and shortened in some cases.

One question that can be asked right in the first meeting is, “What changes have you noticed that have happened since you called to make the appointment for this session?” This question turns the conversation towards solutions very early.

If no changes were noticed, the therapist might ask a different question: “What would need to happen today to make this a really useful session?” This question stays in a solution space. It’s asked from an assumption that a client is able to lead the session. This is curious, because a therapist clearly directs the attention of a client first but then leaves it open for a client to lead. This seems exactly what (Berg & Jong, 2012) call “leading from one step

behind.” It comes from an assumption that communication is co-created by a client and a therapist. Both are active, and both need to agree on where the therapy will go.

What might a therapist ask if the client did notice changes between booking an appointment and coming to the session? One possibility is to ask, “If these changes were to continue in this direction, would this be what you would like?”

This already assists a client to think about their *preferred future*. The assumption is that a client probably has some ideas about what problems they don’t want to have, but questions about what life they would like to live despite the problem need further exploration. What if the client answers that things got worse? One could say, “This sounds hard. How are you managing to cope with this to the degree you are?” or “How have you managed to keep things from getting worse?”

This shows natural empathy but also invites a client to pay closer attention to the ways they manage life, even a little. One could connect this to one of the main principles—*if it works, do more of it*. This question might assume that there are some ways in which the client manages life that ways can be used more frequently. This also assumes that small changes might be enough to compound into a bigger change.

An example of what is called a “miracle question” now will be presented. This is a long question that needs to be asked at the right moment, as (De Shazer et al., 2021) writes, but for the present purposes an abbreviated version will be examined: “... Sometime when you were sleeping... I don’t know what it is, but something shifted...you wake up...your problem is not there...what would your family notice?” This question engages the imagination of a client to come up with an idea of the life they want to live. In that particular example, the last question is asked from the family perspective. It might be done to focus the client on things they might *do* differently. It continues with a simple question to get further details: “What else?” Berg & Jong (2012) emphasizes the high importance of such questions: “Effective solution building requires getting details, details, and more details.”

After co-creating an image of a preferred future, a therapist encourages a client to find *exceptions*, parts of the *preferred future* that are already present. This is an example of such a question that searches for exceptions: “Can you give me an example of the last time you did that?”

At last, it might be curious to see what questions are asked directly about solutions.

Here is an example from a family therapy session: “So let’s make this clear. Anita will try to talk to you more when she comes home from school... Anything else you want to add?” As one can clearly see, the therapist didn’t suggest a solution. Instead, they repeated what solution a client came up with using the client’s own words. The therapist chose to simply highlight it and provided an opportunity to think about it. This further illustrates again how clients are viewed in solution-focused brief therapy — as experts in their own lives.

1.3 Group Solution-Focused Therapy

Prabawa et al. (2025) argues that approaches including both internal and external components improve outcomes of gratitude interventions. They argue that the combination of personal and social elements benefits mental health better than interventions involving one of those elements. At the same time, preliminary findings propose that social group contexts, such as social networking platforms, can amplify the benefits of gratitude (Sciara et al., 2021).

Therefore, combining answering gratitude questions, reading answers of others, and interacting with each other might improve outcomes compared to doing gratitude interventions alone. Therefore, ideas on how to conduct a solution-oriented will be valuable to review.

In this section, questions that a solution-focused therapist could ask in a group setting will be reviewed. Ideas from a book called “Solution Focused Group Therapy” (Metcalf, 2007) will be presented. Group example exercises along with example questions will be presented and connected to the main principles of the approach.

In a group setting, general main principles are still at work (Metcalf, 2007):

1. We help clients to create a picture of a preferred future.
2. We pay attention to moments where a problem isn’t present.
3. We pay attention to all the ways our clients manage life.
4. We stay close to how clients describe what’s important to them.

What’s different then? How can members of a group be helpful to each other? Metcalf (2007) suggests that group members can listen to each other carefully and share what strengths they see in each other.

How is a solution-oriented atmosphere preserved by groups? In a parenting group, Metcalf (2007) opened the group with the question “What brought you here?” Answers were all problem-oriented, like “My daughter does not obey any rules, ever” to “I’m worn out trying.” The author describes that it was hard to balance between hearing parents’ struggles and not letting the group spiral down into desperation. She risked asking how they would like things to be at home as if a miracle had happened. As homework, the parents were assigned to observe anything that might be considered positive in their family. In the next session, some parents brought up a few stories, and Metcalf responded with enthusiasm and asked how that positive exchange happened.

Metcalf (2007) notes that after the first two or three group meetings, a solution-oriented atmosphere comes naturally, and the group starts engaging more and more in a solution-oriented talk. It seems that group join in solution talk rather early.

1.3.1 Group Exercise Example

In the spirit of a solution-oriented approach that puts practice first without much theorizing, let’s take a look at the more structured group exercise and see if main principles can be found in it.

Metcalf (2007) suggests following a group exercise to help the group reflect on the consequences of focusing on strength vs. weaknesses. This exercise directly encourages members to think about a solution-oriented approach.

She invites a group to watch the first 10 minutes of the Home Alone movie. It’s the opening scene where a big extended family is preparing for a trip. Half of the group is instructed to pay attention to the strengths of the family, and another half to the limitations.

After watching, the group writes down what they found on a chalkboard. The group would be facilitated to discuss how easy it was to come up with descriptions of strengths vs. weaknesses. Then, the following questions will be asked:

1. If we brought this family in for consultation with us, which descriptions would give them direction? Why?
2. Can those of you who managed to see strengths amidst the chaos give us an idea of how you did this?

3. If just for a week you all used what we've talked about to see strengths in your own family, what would you be able to think about when times at home become chaotic?

The group is guided to think directly about a solution-oriented approach to life. This helps the group to think through their own approach in life slowly, which may provide a more sustainable shift in their behavior (Albrighton, 2021).

One can imagine how the group dynamic might benefit individuals in the group. The group might come up with more diverse ideas than an individual, and then there are more opportunities to disagree or agree with some ideas. The second question in the list provides an opportunity to show off their skills, which one can imagine does feel good.

1.3.2 Questions Examples

Let's begin with an example of a question that searches for *exceptions*: "Can you share with the group what you did when you successfully resisted the urge to drink?" (Metcalf, 2007). It's worth noting here that "resisted the urge to drink" is the word in which the client themselves describe the exceptions. One also can see here a clear invitation to share something with a group.

The following question again searches for exceptions or resources members use in the group: "What are you believing about yourself here in the group that helped you to change? What's going on that made a difference?" Metcalf (2007) proposes that one can ask group members to describe the behaviors that others display in a group that impress them. Responses can be written on a chalkboard.

One example question to find out what helped make the positive exchange is, "What was the difference that made a difference?" (Metcalf, 2007). It seems to be a very open question that positions clients as experts and helps them find their own resources to manage life.

2 Gratitude-Oriented Digital Communities

In this chapter, what is known about existing research about gratitude-oriented digital communities will be reviewed. Three research projects will be discussed—one mobile app and its effects on reducing repetitive negative thinking, one paper about observing acts of gratitude on social media, and one paper about feedback on using a gratitude-oriented digital community that launched in a university. Description, user feedback, and questions from my own mobile app Gratitude Club will be reviewed.

2.1 Existing Research

In this section, existing research on gratitude-oriented digital communities will be reviewed. It's found to be limited. By searching the phrase “gratitude-oriented digital community” without any filters, only 33 results are showing in Google Scholar. This section will review only 3 papers out of all 5 papers that were relevant for the present thesis.

2.1.1 Reducing Negative Thinking

Kalon et al. (2025) researched the effectiveness of a gratitude app at reducing repetitive negative thinking. The tested app included a feature that enabled sharing moments of gratitude with other people. They found significantly lower levels of repetitive negative thinking among app users. They also found that people that matched the criteria for depression benefited more.

Authors suggest that gratitude apps can be an effective low-threshold intervention able to reach the general population. They warn that interventions that are easy to start are also the ones that are easy to stop (Kalon et al., 2025).

When calculating the effects of a gratitude app, Kalon et al. (2025) mention the following approach for goals for a mental health app. If we target a general audience, we must be careful if we record a small effect size on an individual level, because on a population level, results might be large. To say it clearly, it's best then to accept that most people won't actively use it, but those who will use it will make a difference in the world. A difference is made if enough people improve a little or some people improve meaningfully.

It's also been reported from users' feedback that fixed external goals like asking people to notice 3 or 5 positive things a day can create pressure on users and reduce their enjoyment of using it (Kalon et al., 2025).

Kalon et al. (2025) writes that a better user experience of mental health apps predicts better mental health outcomes.

2.1.2 Observing Grateful Interactions

Sciara et al. (2021) hypothesizes that social media is an interesting context that can potentially aid in spreading gratitude. Social media allows passive observation of others' conversations. Two people might talk to each other, and others can be observing. This provides an opportunity for others to see gratitude expressions of others and be personally affected by that.

Sciara et al. (2021) put that possibility to the test. They created an experiment on Facebook where some people expressed their gratitude, and others were just observing. They found that people who observed grateful expressions on Facebook started expressing their gratitude in person more, but not subjective direct experiences of gratitude. It also was connected to improvement of some aspects of well-being, but not negative and positive affect.

This suggests that observing expressions of gratitude can help people imitate those behaviors, but not necessarily have an intention to cultivate a grateful outlook to life. This draws on Bandura's theory of social learning (Bandura, 1977) that describes how simply observing a behavior helps us learn to imitate it, even without us planning to learn anything.

Another idea that Sciara et al. (2021) mentions is emotional contagion. Emotional contagion is when we change what we do and what we feel simply by observing others' emotional expressions. They also describe previous experiments that give us a first idea based on research on how gratitude can influence groups. Basically, an observer of a gratitude exchange likes both the giver and receiver more and is more ready to help both of them.

Along with a suggestion from different research (Sciara et al., 2021), they suggest that people can feel more positive emotions simply when they observe positive interactions.

Summarizing, how gratitude can work in a digital community:

- people may feel better when they see positive interactions.
- when people are expressing gratitude, observers learn to do the same.
- people like and become more helpful to people who express and receive gratitude.

It's obviously not that simple. Sciara et al. (2021) also notes that in their experiment, there were strangers to each other, and that's maybe why observers' gratitude wasn't measurably increased. It's speculated that emotional reaction to posts depends not only on the content but on a relationship between the author and the reader. A more emotional response is connected to a closer relationship.

It is also speculated that the response to reading a grateful expression might depend on how usually a person reacts to a similar situation. One possibility is to feel gratitude for the person, another possibility is to compare yourself and feel bad (Sciara et al., 2021).

2.1.3 Campus Gratitude Platform

Lei et al. (2025) built a website for campus students that is focused on gratitude. They invited people to use it for 3 weeks and provided them with questions that progressed from less to more vulnerable. Participants were interviewed before they started using the website and asked to fill in special forms before the next set of questions was made available on the website. The goal was to find what participants think about such a platform—what benefits they would find and what would concern them.

Participants were not sure of the value of sharing gratitude publicly. They questioned whether the time they spend doing it is worth it. A low amount of interactions between members was another argument against the value of sharing gratitude publicly. One person mentioned that because there are not many interactions, it wasn't different enough from the experience of writing in one's own private journal (Lei et al., 2025). This highlights the need for facilitated interaction between members. It can be archived with questions.

Members suspected that public gratitude can be less sincere, with less detail and boring to read. It might be connected to other concerns that reflecting on gratitude publicly can be scary because others might judge and misinterpret the message (Lei et al., 2025). If it's scary, members might write more vaguely and with vague descriptions, which is boring

to read (Albrighton, 2021). This can be addressed by reflective questions that ask about concrete people and situations.

Although, when a participant posted about one specific person, he felt bad about not choosing to write about others. It was hard to decide on someone (Lei et al., 2025).

Members also reported that they needed to select the words of their posts carefully. It was hard not to see an intimidating reaction that one might see in face-to-face interactions to possibly correct what you say (Lei et al., 2025).

Questions Lei et al. (2025) asked in their online gratitude community will be discussed. Members of this community were students on the same campus. Mostly the questions that are different from examples previously reviewed are for gratitude interventions and ones that are special for this platform.

This is what might be considered a “classic gratitude question” adapted to the platform: “What are you most grateful for about your campus or your campus experience?” Curiously here, since all members are on the same campus, this question provides an opportunity to create additional communication between members because they can relate to each other’s experiences on the campus.

This question also provides an opportunity for communication between members, but additionally there is a chance that someone will express gratitude towards a person who is also on the platform: “Who is someone you’re grateful for at campus (or elsewhere) and why?”

Another example question directly invites a member to interact with another member in the community: “Find a gratitude note someone else wrote that resonates with you and share something that it makes you grateful for”.

Although all questions mentioned invite members to interact with each other, one member of this community noted in their interview that there were not many interactions. This community was designed as most social media are designed now—there were posts from individual members and the ability to like and comment on them. The current version of my own Gratitude Club app is structured that way also, and one member of my club also shared that they wish the app had more interactions between members.

2.2 Gratitude Club App

In 2025, I created an iPhone app called Gratitude Club, a group-based app that helps people reflect on gratitude together. Members of the app post gratitude reflections and can interact with each other by commenting on or liking others's posts. The app is largely inspired by reflective questions from the book "Gratitude Works!" by Robert Emmons (2013), a prominent researcher and author in the field. It was publicly available, and people could find it on Apple's App Store. Gratitude Club was described as a group reflection app that helps people to reflect on gratitude together.

People download the app, read a bit more about it, and make a decision about whether they want to pay for its membership. If they choose to, they set up a profile, mention their name, and upload their photo. Immediately after that, they can read what others have been grateful for. They can tap the "Reflect" button, and a chat-like interface shows up. They see a first question that is the same for all people in the app on that date. "Who do you want to reach out to today to express your gratitude?" for example. The member types their answer, and the large language model comes up with a next question based on my instructions. For example, if the user answered "My friend Kevin," the question "In what way would you like to express your gratitude to Kevin?" can be asked. The chat goes up to 11 questions, but a user can tap the "Wrap up" button anytime to go to the next step. On that next step, all user answers get combined, the user can edit the whole reflection text, and share it with the Gratitude Club.

The following reflective questions were asked in the app:

- Who offered a small kindness, paid attention when it mattered, smiled at you, or helped you with something?
- The world places countless gifts at our feet, though they often slip by unseen. What gift stands out to you today?
- Think of this club as your personal playground for relating to others. What small experiment could you try today? Perhaps a reflection from another member caught your attention, or someone inspired you. Whose words touched you in some way?
- Imagine if someone or something were absent from your life. What if a person in your life today had never been part of it? Or perhaps something in your life (a

project, experience, or phase) is actually coming to an end. Who or what comes to mind?

- Who do you want to reach out to today to express your gratitude?
- Think of your worst moments, your losses, and your hardest days. Reflect on how you made your way out of the dark, faced temptation, or got through a difficult phase. Can you recall an experience like that you feel grateful for now?

Members of this app in private conversations with me described how the app helped them and where it could be improved. It was mentioned that the app helped them notice more good things around them and helped them find positive aspects in events they previously considered as negative. Reflections of others and notifications were perceived as reminders to slow down and notice more good.

There were several comments about reflective questions in the app. Seeing the same questions every week was perceived as unhelpful. More questions were requested. One participant said that sometimes questions were too specific and expressed the need for more open-ended questions.

Additionally, members commented on community dynamics. One member specifically stopped their membership because of the lack of an engaged community. Another suggested that she would be more comfortable sharing reflections in mini-groups that consisted mostly of people she knew.

Words like “forced” and “pushed” were used in the comments about the app. Members sometimes felt forced to appreciate more. Although this has been said not with a negative connotation, this still shows that the app was leading members to its own way. While this was characterized as desirable, it raises concerns about whether there was a mismatch between the user’s goals and the app’s offering.

The lack of an engaged community and expressed desire to share reflections with a small group of friends might be simply explained by the fact that there were very few people in the app to create an engaged community to connect with. This also may be read as a call for better facilitation—better questions that adapt to more diverse goals. That might help people open up more and connect to others who have similar goals. This is what possible integration of gratitude interventions with solution-focused brief therapy can address.

3 Shaping Questions with SFBT for a Group-Based Gratitude Mobile App

Evidence highlights mobile apps as an effective, low-cost, scalable way to deliver gratitude interventions and proposes that social group contexts can amplify the benefits of gratitude. However, it has been emphasized that apps should adapt better to diverse user contexts. After reviewing literature on solution-focused brief therapy, gratitude interventions, and gratitude-oriented digital communities, this chapter explores possible integration of those three. In existing literature, both integration of solution-focused brief therapy and gratitude interventions or integration of group solution-focused brief therapy in digital interventions are not found.

In this chapter, tensions between SFBT and gratitude will be discussed along with two ideas of possible integration of the approaches, resolving with possible questions that an integrated approach could use.

3.1 Resolving Tensions Between SFBT And Gratitude Approaches

One obvious tension is that in solution-focused brief therapy *solutions* are co-created by therapists and clients (Berg & Jong, 2012) and in gratitude interventions, *gratitude itself* seems to be a solution if gratitude interventions are viewed through the lens of SFBT. Although it seems like gratitude was never claimed to be a solution to all problems by any literature reviewed.

Nonetheless, examples of gratitude questions and examples of SFBT felt different. Examples of gratitude questions were taken from self-help books, and SFBT questions were usually taken from the context of a session, and that's why they might feel different. When someone opens "The Little Book of Gratitude" of Emmons (2024), the book has no context of the person's life and their goals. Those questions are similar to what a solution-focused therapist might ask at the beginning of the first session, because they give direction right away without knowing much context about a person. In contrast, SFBT questions that were reviewed in the present paper were often positioned in a concrete situation where they made sense. In contrast to them, gratitude questions might seem like they push or

prescribe the gratitude as a solution to everything, but because the media through which it was delivered doesn't know the context. Therefore, these contextless questions are not a characteristic of questions themselves but of a medium via which they were delivered. That means that the tension between SFBT questions and gratitude questions was also due to the context in which they were taken from, and that tension should be discarded when shaping new questions for the app.

Important tension might have to do with connecting personal goals to an approach. SFBT as an approach seems to suit all kinds of goals, but gratitude interventions seem to only suit the goal of practicing gratitude. Even if Emmons (2024) says that gratitude connects, and someone tries gratitude interventions with a goal of connecting with others, it might not work out well for a person. Because gratitude isn't a magic pill that connects people without any other complications. Still, one can imagine that if one comes to an app with the goal of practicing gratitude, gratitude questions will be felt as relevant and maybe even inspiring. That may explain in part why some people find it difficult to articulate the importance of gratitude in their life when asked. It might be simple, because they don't have a goal to be grateful in their mind.

That said, even if someone is trying gratitude intervention or even joining an app called *Gratitude Club*, they do not necessarily have an intention of practicing gratitude. They might be just curious. Or they might hope that gratitude can help them feel less alone, but the intention of "feeling less alone" is still different from the goal of practicing gratitude. Therefore, one could speculate that a new integrated approach could suit a broader range of intentions.

Ideally, gratitude questions provide a person that already has an intention of practicing gratitude with an idea or two of how to practice that intention. That is similar to the SFBT idea of "leading from behind" (Berg & Jong, 2012). If a person has a different intention, SFBT questions could be offered to help the person to form their own solutions. Knowing that a person joined an app called *Gratitude Club* willingly, this context can be brought up in questions to help members reflect.

Another important tension is that it is promptly given to us by philosopher Herman, who describes gratitude as one duty in the system of duties. She basically says, Gratitude alone is not enough! One can see this tension in gratitude questions. In gratitude, it may

seem that questions are focused on what *others have done*, and in SFBT, it's about what *you* have done. One seems to be related to connection and safety, and the other to autonomy and agency. Yet in the reviewed example questions, both gratitude questions ask what somebody has done personally, and SFBT questions ask about what made the difference in general. Both approaches can help to build self-agency and connection to others. One can see that there is not much tension in that regard in both approaches.

Also, it seems essential to talk about the tension regarding the goal of a new integrated intervention. Kalon et al. (2025) when investigating a gratitude app, reported that because it's so easy to start in such an intervention, it can also be easy to stop. That can be seen as a problem, as something to overcome. The SFBT idea is different. If a client did decide to stop, it can be just their choice, not a fault of therapy. If the concern with which you initially came is not bothering you as much as before, why continue (Berg & Jong, 2012)? It seems like the goal of a new integrated intervention is not to keep people as much as possible until they reach some desired effect that was set by a creator of the intervention or by a researcher. A better goal would be to help people reflect so they take whatever they need and let them choose when to leave and when to come back. This seems close to what a minimalist approach like SFBT would have in mind (McKergow & Korman, 2009).

3.2 Integration of Approaches

In a previous section, multiple tensions between approaches have been resolved. In this section, a few possible options for integration will be discussed along with a few principles that could fit the new integrated approach.

It's important to mention that even if solution-focused brief therapy is integrated, the app can not be viewed as a psychotherapy. Gratitude Club, like other mental health apps, can be viewed as a non-direct supportive treatment (Kalon et al., 2025).

One principle from SFBT that can be integrated with gratitude into a new approach is *small steps lead to big changes* (De Shazer et al., 2021). Noticing a bit of appreciation towards one friend in one situation might lead to a completely new way of relating to people with time. Asking about ways one wishes to express gratitude might not lead to drastic changes now but might to bigger changes later on. Therefore, questions do need to be asked about big changes, and even simply exploring different solutions (for example,

regarding how one wishes to express gratitude) could be helpful.

Another principle that seems to be common for SFBT and gratitude is *if it works, do more of it*, or *gratitude amplifies*. Gratitude interventions are good at helping people pay attention to what works for them, and SFBT is also inviting people to see the good in their lives. This principle can be taken as is for the new integrated approach.

One may even suggest that positive interactions in the group could have the same characteristics as gratitude in the ARC model of Emmons (2024). A group-based gratitude app can amplify the good, rescue people from feeling bad, and connect people to each other and to others in their lives. This model can become a model for the new integrated approach.

One possible integration of the two approaches is to think of gratitude as one possible topic or a part of a person's *preferred future*. This integration simply adds the topic of gratitude to solution-focused conversation. One can imagine that if a user joins an app with a name like Gratitude Club, they might want to try gratitude practice. However, whether there is an intention to practice gratitude, one never knows, and if SFBT ideas would be a foundation, questions can help to explore whether gratitude is part of the preferred future for a particular person. Maybe members will decide that in their good version of a future, they practice gratitude more, and then the app can facilitate that with questions from gratitude interventions. If a member decides that gratitude is part of their solution, questions might invite them to pay more attention to moments when they do express gratitude, for example. Perhaps members would want to be more attentive to kind gestures of their friends to be closer to them, and new questions can help them reflect on that.

Another, more radical integration might be to create a gratitude-oriented atmosphere right away in the group. Metcalf (2007) notes that after 2 or 3 sessions of conducting solution-oriented groups, group atmosphere becomes more solution-oriented. That could mean that as Metcalf's groups join in a solution frame, members of my app will slowly join in to a gratitude-oriented frame. That has been my experience with a current version of the app. In fact, this is exactly what people are searching for—new ways to look at life with gratitude. In that idea of integration, gratitude orientation is set up right away, and later questions are taken from SFBT to keep that gratitude frame.

How could questions be shaped practically in the mobile app context? In a group ther-

any format, a therapist can shape questions on the go pay attention to the goals and needs of every member, but in the app context, this might not be possible. One solution is to use large language models to adapt questions to the context of users. A recent paper (Lewis & Hayhoe, 2024) investigated using large language models to help general practitioners foster deeper self-reflection by instructing the models to create thought-provoking questions. It was concluded that the models can complement personal reflection. It's suggesting that using them is a viable path. De Shazer et al. (2021) proposes that SFBT cannot be applied formally and adaptation of methods to clients is needed. Current large language models seem to provide an opportunity to adapt questions to users's contexts.

Should questions in the app directly facilitate group interactions? One member of a digital community recommended directly that limited interactions between members made the experience on the platform not much different from the experience of writing a private diary. It's also been recommended that people may feel better when they see positive interactions; they will learn to repeat such interactions in their life, which is desirable (Sciara et al., 2021). Given that interactions between members are probably why people will join Gratitude Club and that it could provide benefits, it makes sense that questions in the app should at least partly directly facilitate interactions between members. This includes asking specific members questions, inviting people to work in pairs, or providing an opportunity for everyone to be heard.

However, one can imagine that even if interactions won't be specifically inviting interactions between members but asking the group in general, it could also provide benefits. Gratitude may become like a shared inspiration. By joining the app, people express that gratitude is a part of their *preferred future* vision. Part of the app can be customizable to users' goals, and fundamentally, it'll be gratitude-oriented. The value of living gratefully can unite and connect people.

It would be useful for later research to name that new integrated approach. It will be referred to as a *gratitude-oriented approach*. The gratitude-oriented approach invites members into a gratitude frame right in the beginning, uses solution-focused brief therapy as a basis, invites reflection about whether gratitude can be a part of a preferred future or a solution, and facilitates group reflections.

3.3 Question Examples for a Group-Based Gratitude Mobile App

Building on the idea that questions need to be new to inspire and that a gratitude-oriented atmosphere can be established in the app right away, the following question might be asked: “Even just starting, how has joining this space affected you so far?”

If nothing is affected by a person, a slightly adapted question from SFBT works here: “What would need to happen here for this first week to feel valuable for you?”

Whenever people bring up problems in their reflection, it might be helpful to use a classic SFBT question to turn a conversation towards solution talk: “This sounds hard. How are you managing to cope with this to the degree you are?”

One principle of SFBT is that a question must follow what clients said before (Berg & Jong, 2012). The following question demonstrates how a question can be born out of previous reflections and continue to embrace gratitude orientation and is directly inspired by gratitude intervention from Emmons (2024) and also applies an SFBT principle: *small steps lead to big changes*: “Recently, some reflections mentioned moments of appreciation. I wonder, where else do you notice feeling joy, even if a little?”

When someone reads a reflection of the other person, a “Reflect” button could be shown next to that reflection. Tapping can lead to another screen with a following question that invites interaction between members: “Which part of Kathy’s words speaks to you?”

Once again building on what others have said, but now using more of SFBT-style question that focuses on what worked before, following question can be asked to a whole group: “Last week, we reflected on who we give our energy to. Who have you given energy to that felt good, and what was different about it?”

Another group-focused SFBT question that might be asked of members who have been using the app for a while: “Now that you’ve been part of the group for a month, what are you believing about yourself here in the group that helped you? What’s going on that made a difference?”

Not only asking individual questions is possible, but also structured exercises that organize the interaction differently. Inspired by Metcalf (2007) exercise where people watched part of Home Alone to see the family’s strengths and weaknesses, one could imagine this exercise with gratitude in mind. A group in the app can watch the same part of the Home Alone movie, split into two groups. One would watch for the things they

appreciate about the family, another one for things they don't like. They can list their findings in the app and then discuss. The following questions might be asked to a group, and their answers made visible to all members:

1. What did you appreciate about the family?
2. What did you not like about it?
3. How easy was it to come up with descriptions of appreciations vs. things you didn't like?
4. Which descriptions would you say would be useful for them to hear? Why?
5. Can those of you who manage to see strengths amidst the chaos give us an idea of how you did this?
6. If just for a week you all used what we've talked about in your own family, what would you suggest that you could think about when times at home become chaotic?

This exercise is a good demonstration that sometimes there is not much difference between a grateful outlook on life and what solution-focused therapists invite to reflect on.

Conclusion

In this thesis, possible integration of solution-focused brief therapy and gratitude interventions in order to shape reflective questions for a group-based mobile app was explored and found to be both possible and promising. Combining solution-focused brief therapy and gratitude approaches is promising because it would allow addressing a broader range of people's goals than using just gratitude questions while still responding to widespread interest in gratitude practices. This thesis provides ideas on how to organize group-based mobile app intervention using a new integrated gratitude-oriented approach. It presents questions that might be asked to the whole group, suggests how to facilitate interactions between members, and suggests how to adapt questions to the user's context.

This thesis presents the first attempt to integrate gratitude interventions with solution-focused brief therapy and group solution-focused brief therapy in the context of a mobile app. This work offers conceptual ideas and example questions for digital group-based interventions that may be used as a standalone intervention or alongside psychotherapy. Practically, this paper provides new ideas for designing digital mental health apps in more user-centric ways.

Despite these contributions, this paper has several important limitations. Firstly, books that we reviewed in this thesis may only reflect the authors' individual approaches and therefore might not represent well how each approach is understood or practiced broadly. Secondly, the new integrated gratitude-oriented approach needs practical and scientific investigation.

Future research could adopt a mixed-methods approach similar to how authors of solution-focused brief therapy developed their approach by observation and noting what questions are helping people move closer towards their goals. It might involve thematically coding users's responses to different questions and counting times users moved closer towards their own goals. This approach might provide useful feedback that would later inform further development of digital mental health interventions.

I believe it's critical to create mental health apps with good care. This paper is a call for revising how mental health digital interventions are designed and a call for researchers and psychotherapists to join the process of creating new group-based digital interventions.

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Academic Integrity Statement

I declare that I have written this thesis without any outside help and that I have used only the literature, sources, materials, aids and technical tools (e.g. artificial intelligence [AI] tools) specified in the text. The literature, sources, materials, aids and technical tools used in this work have been documented in accordance with SFU guidelines and standards of good research practice. I also declare that this work has never been submitted to any other higher education institution or university, in any other language, or as part of any other program or course.

Vienna,

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Signature

Step	Use	Software	Version
General idea and outline	Brainstormed for ideas and structure of the thesis	ChatGPT	4o
Literature search	Looked for publications on the research topic	ChatGPT	4o & 5
Literature search	Looked for publications on the research topic	Google Scholar	2025-2026
Managing references	Organizing references	Zotero	7.0
Text formatting	Formatting headlines, citations and tables	Zettlr	4.1
Translation	Translation of the abstract into German	ChatGPT	5
Copy editing and prooreading	Revision of the entire text	Apple Intelligence	MacOS Tahoe

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